

Evidence - Based Review of the Risk Factors for the Development of Anaemia and Leukopenia in the Treatment of HCV Infection with Pegylated - Interferon and Ribavirin

The development of a haemolytic anaemia and leukopenia are common side effects of the standard regimen of treatment for HCV infected individuals with Pegylated-Interferon and Ribavirin [1]. Risk factors for the development of both are well known and this review underscores each of them beginning with the development of anaemia. Risk factors associated with the development of anaemia are concerned firstly, with Ribavirin dose, with the probability of anaemia increasing as a function of Ribavirin dose, 6-16% in one study with an increase in the dose of Ribavirin from 12-16 mg kg⁻¹ [2]. This becomes a problem in relation to the different HCV genotypes, as an SVR in genotype 1 is dose dependent with higher doses resulting in a better SVR in comparison to genotypes 2 and 3 [2]. Another predisposing factor in the development of anaemia is lower baseline haemoglobin upon therapy initiation [2]. The PRESCO Team showed that lower baseline haemoglobin [RR: 0.14 (95% CI 0.07-0.27); P<0.0001] and greater haemoglobin drops during the first 4 weeks of therapy (also associated with a lower baseline Hb) [RR: 4.74 (95% CI 2.95-7.60); P<0.0001] were independent predictors of moderate anaemia (Hb<10g/dl) [3]. In the case of HCV/HIV co-infected individuals, the use of Zidovudine (an NRTI) in conjunction with the HCV treatment regimen further precipitates drops in baseline haemoglobin, and this may in itself be considered yet another independent predictor of anaemia development [3]. Phase 3 trials on the newer drugs Boceprevir and Telaprevir have both been shown to be more efficacious with regard SVR, but they have also been shown to be stronger predictors of anaemia as the rates of anaemia in patients receiving them increase from 17%-27%, with 4% having severe anaemia (Hb<8.5g/dl) [6]. Other factors which may lead to anaemia development include; sex(F>M), age(incidence increases with age), baseline ALT quotient and cirrhosis [2,3]

Leukopenia is associated with bone marrow suppression in HCV infected individuals and results from treatment with the glycoprotein Pegylated-Interferon . Pegylated Interferon therapy can be initiated using the alpha-2a type, or alpha-2b type, with higher incidences of bone marrow suppression resulting in treatment with the alpha-2a type [4]. According to another study in which 142 HCV-infected patients received peginterferon-alpha2a plus ribavirin, a baseline neutrophil count below 2050/mm³ (HR: 3.59; 95% CI: 1.77-7.28) and baseline weight <60 kg (HR: 2.21; 95% CI: 1.04-4.56) were independently associated with the development of neutropenia (with 22.5% of patients reaching the neutrophil-endpoint all of which possessed the adequate baseline criteria) [5]. The same

study revealed that a baseline platelet count (x1000/mm³) decrease) (HR: 1.074; 95% CI: 1.04-1.11) was independently associated with the development of thrombocytopenia (7% of patients reaching the platelet-endpoint) [5].

To conclude, treatment regimens and baseline factors allow the identification of a subset of HCV-infected patients who are prone to experience haematological toxicity during HCV antiviral therapy.

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[1] **Hepatitis C virus treatment-related anemia is associated with higher sustained virologic response rate.**

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Predicting sustained virological response and anaemia in chronic hepatitis C patients treated with peginterferon alfa-2a (40KD) plus ribavirin.

Snoeck E, Wade JR, Duff F, Lamb M, Jorga K.

Source

Exprimo NV, Lummen, Belgium, F. Hoffmann-La Roche Nutley, NJ, USA.

[3] Br J Clin Pharmacol. 2006 Dec;62(6):699-709.

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Predictors of severe haematological toxicity secondary to pegylated interferon plus ribavirin treatment in HIV-HCV-coinfected patients.

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